

The Effect of Target Model Facetization on RCS Predictions

E. M. Miller, D. J. Andersh, A. J. Terzuoli Jr.
Air Force Institute of Technology
Wright-Patterson AFB Ohio

1 Abstract

Xpatch V4.0¹ is a Radar Signature prediction code that provides both frequency domain radar cross section predictions and time domain results for a flat faceted triangular geometry file. It is a fully polarimetric code that performs monostatic and bistatic predictions and provides the capability to rotate facets, calculate shadowing and blockage, perform multibounce calculations, and calculate scattering from radar absorbing materials (RAM). The prediction method is based on the Shooting Bouncing Ray method, Physical Optics and Physical Theory of Diffraction to obtain the target scattered field.

This paper² presents the effects of 3-D model facetization on the radar signature predicted by Xpatch. Predictions were compared against exact and measured data for two primitives and one complex target. By changing the level of flat facetization on the same geometry file, the signature prediction can vary dramatically.

2 Introduction

Before Xpatch is used to predict the radar signature of flat facetized models, the limitations of the flat facet approach must be understood because measurements we use as reference are not always exact. There is an uncertainty associated with the target's position when it is put on the rotator in the measurement chamber. Depending on the care taken, and measurement equipment used, the target's position could easily be off by 1° or 2° in both azimuth and elevation. With a great deal more time and effort, a more accurate alignment could be accomplished using a HeNe LASER for example. These small changes in position can have sizable effects on the measured azimuth scans and range

¹A High Frequency RCS Computation Code for Flat Patches with interactions, written by S. W. Lee of the University of Illinois

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profiles. Therefore, predictions cannot be judged blindly against the measured data. A target with an exact solution, such as a sphere should be used to weight against Xpatch predictions to provide a baseline from which to build. A test was conducted to evaluate Xpatch's frequency response prediction of a 6" sphere with four different facetization levels. In addition, the effect on the azimuth scan of an almond and the range profile of a complex missile were evaluated.

3 Results

This paper presents the results of a facetization study performed on three models.

3.1 Sphere

A 6" sphere was chosen to test the frequency response prediction capability. CAD/CAM models were built for the same geometry by increasing the number of facets in each. The final values were:

- sphere 1 360 facets
- sphere 2 1,520 facets
- sphere 3 3,480 facets
- sphere 4 9,800 facets

Figure 1: Sphere with 360, 1520, 3480, and 9800 Flat Facets

Figure 1 shows the variations in the predictions for each sphere from a look angle of 45° azimuth and 45° elevation over a large frequency band. Three other look angles were used but this one provided the best overall response. All predictions were compared against the exact Mie series for the sphere, with the highest facetization deviating very little.

3.2 Almond

The effect of facetization on azimuth, for an almond with dimensions: $l=9.936''$, $h=1.28''$, $w=3.842''$, was addressed. In order to ensure at least five wavelengths over the target as recommended by Knott[1], the prediction was made at 18 GHz. The following three facetization levels were used:

coarse 454 facets
medium 8,032 facets
fine 29,394 facets

Figure 2: Almond Effect Of Facetization Level

Figure 2 shows the variation in the Xpatch prediction for the three facetization levels of the almond. Each prediction was evaluated, at two frequencies, against bench marked primitive measurements made by China Lake in conjunction with NASA AMES Research Center[3].

3.3 Scale AIM-9

To test the effect on time domain range profile predictions, three model files were built for the 1/3.72 scale AIM-9 with the following facetizations:

coarse 2,758 facets with 294 edges
medium 4,246 facets with 326 edges
fine 9,706 facets with 458 edges

The variations in the predicted range profiles, for each facetization, are shown in Figure 3. The predicted data was evaluated against measured of a physical model built to match the geometry file. The measurements were taken in the compact range at The Ohio State University[2].

Figure 3: AIM-9 Range Profile VS Facetization

4 Conclusions

Xpatch V4.0 uses flat faceted geometry files to predict the radar signature. Clearly, the flat faceted model has problems associated with it. If this type of geometry is to be used in the prediction of a doubly curved target, care must be taken to understand how the facets are laid out on the CAD/CAM model. If not, the results could have a larger error associated with them than anticipated. The test results show that a higher number of facets gives a better prediction, but, it comes at the expense of CPU time. Since faster run times are desired, care must be taken in building the geometry files to strike a balance between speed and accuracy.

References

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